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**STUDY HABITS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF EDUCATION STUDENTS IN
ISABELA STATE UNIVERSITY ECHAGUE CAMPUS**

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the study habits and the academic performance of BEED students of Isabela State University-Echague Campus. The respondents were 78 Fourth-Year students of the Bachelor of Elementary Education who were enrolled during the First and Second Semesters of the School Year 2021-2022.

The data were gathered using the survey research design. The results showed that there was a positive relationship between the academic performance and the study habits of the respondents concerning a spacious room with good ventilation and other equipment such as chairs and table, studying with no distractions in the surroundings, social media, and environment, and study techniques like taking down notes in own words, highlighting important words, studying up to 3 hours, having a study time table, and studying with friends but less verbal.

Keywords: Study Habits, Academic Performance, Online Class, New Normal, Synchronous Setting

INTRODUCTION

The most significant predictor of academic achievement is study habits, and global research has shown that study habits impact academic performance, according to Jafari et al. (2019).

According to Alex (2011), a study habit is an activity that students undertake frequently and routinely to complete the job of learning, such as reading, taking notes, or holding study groups. Whether or not they benefit pupils, study habits can be classified as successful or ineffective (Jato, 2013).

Due to the pandemic, everything has changed, including the study habits. The study habits in the new normal are staying organized, avoiding multitasking, setting a schedule, working with a group or team, staying connected to other people, taking notes, using mnemonics, using the pomodoro technique, and scanning notes, among others.

Every student has unique study habits. To develop effective study habits, one must have a strong desire to learn and possess all of one's abilities and talents. In everything, students should have more interest and self-discipline. Good study habits are beneficial to students since they (habits) support students in achieving mastery in areas of specialization

and, as a result, exceptional performance. In contrast, the opposites act as barriers to learning and achievement (Tope, 2011).

Furthermore, according to Lee (2010), effective study habits are vital for students, particularly college or university students, whose needs include time management, note-taking, internet skills, elimination of distractions, and assignment of a high priority to study (Abban, 2012; Arora, 2016; Boch & Piolat, 2005; Deore, 2012; Nagaraju, 2004; Ogbodo, 2010). On the other hand, poor study habits are those that do not work and do not assist pupils in achieving their studies (Bhat & Khandai, 2016). One of the most serious and chronic issues among high school and college students is poor study habits. Poor study habits include poor attendance, note-taking, time management, procrastination, and a lack of attention when studying (Capan, 2010; Muraina, Nyorere, Eman, & Muraina, 2014; Nagaraju, 2004; Ogbodo, 2010; Singh, 2015; Angkarini, 2021)

The findings of studies on study habits as a function of age and gender have been fascinating and enlightening, yet they have varied from one study to the other. For example, in the study of Aluja & Blanch (2004), girls scored higher on a study habits measure. Yet, in the study of Robinson (2018), masculine qualities were found to be more strongly connected to efficient study habits than feminine ones.

On the other hand, Kagu (2003) and Ossai's (2004) research showed no significant differences in male and female students' study patterns.

However, the result of the study of Awabil, Kolo, Bello and Oliagbo (2013) is in contrast with the findings of this research study as it found that there was no significant difference between male and female students in good study habit skills. This research study explored study habits. It was concluded that female students had better study habits than male students and had good performance in their academic life.

On the other hand, parents' socio-economic status (SES) and educational agencies play an important role in shaping the study students' habits at all levels of schooling.

Study habits, combined with the right environment, feedback, and guidance, aid in developing a balanced personality. Teachers should guide students in their study habits at school, while parents should guide their children at home. As a result, it is the responsibility of teachers and parents to identify and guide students' good study habits. An individual's study habits and socio-economic status are inextricably linked. They are proportional to each other and can be thought of as two sides of the same coin. If either of these factors is missing or has been missing, an individual's personality development will be incomplete (Khan, 2016). Additionally, adolescents from higher socio-economic backgrounds have better study habits than those from lower socio-economic backgrounds. (Razia, 2015)

One of the variables to consider as effective study habits that impact student performance is the study environment. According to Kim (2013), a study environment includes a conducive and pleasant area for students to study without noise or interruptions and study resources that are easily accessible to students. "Students learn better if they are in a neat environment with readily available materials, devoid of noise and distractions so they can focus and think about academic problems whether at home or school.

Meanwhile, gender is a socially constructed concept. Male and female characteristics are distinct. Scholars, politicians, and practitioners have seen and seemed to agree on socially constructed gender disparities and their major effects on people's lives. According to studies conducted around the world, there is a large gender disparity in academic achievement among students studying at various levels. According to several studies, female pupils outperform their male counterparts (Orabi, 2007; Dayioglu & Turut, 2007; Khwaileh & Zaza, 2010). Ghazvini and Khajehpour (2011) claimed that even in the academic setting, gender differences in cognitive performance occur. Girls are more likely to adjust to learning in a new situation than boys. In a survey of secondary school pupils in Kenya, Wangu (2014) discovered that boys passed more exams than girls. In contrast, Goni et al. (2015) found no evidence of the effect in a study of college students.

In addition, Ossai's (2012) study showed a significant difference in the students' study habits based on age and gender (Abdullahi, 2014). The result validates the study findings of Awabil, Kolo, Bello and Oliagbo (2013) who found no significant difference between male and female students in terms of good study habit skills. However, the result of this study is in disagreement with another research study that showed that there was a significant difference in the skills of study habits on a gender basis (Ossai, 2012; Saleem et al., 2020).

Furthermore, parents' socio-economic situation impacts not just their children's academic success but also their own. It is conceivable for children from poor socio-economic backgrounds to compete successfully with their peers from higher socio-economic backgrounds.

Education is an important part of one's life. A development tool broadens brains, distinguishes good and wrong, and teaches us to distinguish properly between them. It uses our surroundings to better a person and the group (Sabzwari, 2004). A wealth of materials demonstrates the influence of socio-economic status on health.

As revealed by Suleman et al. (2012), academic achievement discovered that children with good academic performance and those with a higher socioeconomic status perform better academically than those with a lower socioeconomic status. They have weak and substandard academic achievement due to their social position. Saifi (2011) explained the impact of a student's socioeconomic position on their performance was explored.

Finally, one of the most important metrics used to assess the quality of education in universities is student academic achievement. Academic success is a complicated process that is impacted by various factors, including study habits. Study habits are various individual actions in connection to studying and are a combination of study technique and skill. In other words, study habits are behaviors and skills that can boost motivation and transform studying into an effective process with high returns, resulting in increased learning. This ability may also be described as any action that aids in the process of learning about a topic, solving difficulties, or memorizing a portion or all of the contents offered. Study habits, which differ from person to person, are the key to success.

According to prior research, healthy study habits include studying in a quiet environment, studying regularly, and turning off gadgets that interfere with learning (such as cell phones), thereby ensuring a higher academic performance. (Jafari H, 2019)

Moreover, Vargas et al. (2020) found out that students' desks/tables and chairs and the technical equipment they use to study (tablet, cell phone, computer) are examples of such variables that have an impact on a higher academic achievement. Lighting, noise, and temperature are other factors.

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to delve into the study habits and its interaction with the academic performance of Bachelor of Elementary Education students.

Specifically, the study sought to determine the following:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Sex; and
 - b. Family Income?
2. What are the study habits of the respondents in the new normal education?
3. What is the academic performance of the respondents?
4. What is the difference in the study habits of the respondents in the new normal education when they are grouped according to profile (sex)?
5. What is the relationship between the study habits of the respondents in the new normal education and their profile (family monthly income)?
6. What is the relationship between the academic performance and study habits of the respondents in the new normal education?

Scope and Limitation

This study focused on the study habits and academic performance of the Fourth-Year Bachelor of Elementary Education students at Isabela State University-Main Campus. The variables in this study were the socio-demographic status of the respondents, study habits, and academic performance.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational design was used in this study, in which data gathered were recorded, described, interpreted, analyzed, and compared to provide adequate information on the respondents' study habits and its interaction with their academic performance.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the students of the Bachelor of Elementary Education program of Isabela State University-Echague Campus who were enrolled during the First Semester of SY 2021-2022. They were randomly selected using proportional allocation with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error.

Research Instrument

The research instrument was adopted from the study of Dankyi et al., (2014) titled "*An Investigation into the Study Habits of Distance Learners: Implication for Guidance and Counseling Services*". There are two parts to the questionnaire. The first one is the background of the respondents

specifically the name, sex, GWA, and monthly income of the family. The second part is the checklist of the study habits.

Statistical Tools and Treatment

1. Frequency distribution and mean were used to describe the profile of the respondents, their academic performance, and their study habits.
2. T-test was utilized to measure the difference in the study habits of the respondents when they are grouped according to their sex.
3. Pearson's-r correlation was employed to find the relationship between the study habits of the respondents and their academic performance and family income.

Research Framework

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, and Monthly Income.

Variables	Frequency n=78	Percent
SEX		
• Male	8	10.30
• Female	70	89.70
MONTHLY INCOME		
• 500 - 2,000	14	17.90
• 2,001 - 5,000	22	28.20
• 5,001 - 10,000	24	30.80
• 10,001 - 20,000	14	17.90
• Above 20,000	4	5.10

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of sex and monthly family income. In terms of sex, the majority of the respondents are female, accounting for 70 or 89.70% of the total sample, while male respondents account for 8 or 10.30%.

The table also shows that most of the respondents belong to a family with a monthly income of P5,001 – P10,000 and P2,001 – P5,000, constituting 24 or 30.80% and 22 or 28.20% of the total sample, respectively. Meanwhile, 14 or 17.90% of the respondents belong to the families with a monthly income of P500 – P2,000 and P10,001 – P20,000. Lastly, only 4 or 5.10% of the respondents belong to a family with a monthly income above P20,000.

Study Habits of the Respondents in the New Normal

Table 2 describes the habits of the respondents in the new normal.

As gleaned from Table 2, the respondents agree on the different study habits in the new normal as indicated by the grand mean of 2.98. Similarly, the respondents also agree mostly on the study habits dealing with taking down notes during the virtual discussion, using their own words when taking notes, highlighting important words or phrases in books, studying for three hours or more in a day, and having a personal study timetable by their mean ranging from 3.49 to 3.14.

This means that to get good grades in the new normal, students must prioritize their studies despite the pandemic that students encounter nowadays by having study techniques that are helpful enough to maintain good grades.

Table 2. Study Habits of the Respondents in the New Normal

Study Habits	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. My study room is more spacious with good ventilation.	3.08	Agree
2. I do not feel comfortable reading in bed.	2.99	Agree
3. I have a chair and a desk in my study room.	3.01	Agree
4. I do not enjoy studying with music.	2.77	Agree
5. I take down important notes during virtual discussion.	3.49	Agree
6. I highlight important words or phrases in my book when studying.	3.37	Agree
7. I am able to study up to three hours or more in a day.	3.17	Agree
8. I do have a personal study time table.	3.14	Agree
9. I use my own words when taking down note.	3.38	Agree
10. I do not spend much time on social activities at the expense of my studies.	3.03	Agree
11. I do not study few hours before examination.	2.45	Disagree
12. I study with my friends but with less verbal conversation.	2.87	Agree
13. I do not bother myself with personal problems when studying.	2.76	Agree
14. I never doze off when studying.	2.68	Agree
15. I am never attracted to the TV set and other family activities when studying.	2.53	Agree
GRAND MEAN	2.98	AGREE

The results somehow are related to the discussion (Jato, 2013). According to Alex (2011) study habit pertains to actions such as reading, taking notes, and holding study groups which the students perform regularly and habitually to accomplish the task of learning. Study habits can be described as effective or ineffective depending upon whether or not they serve the students well.

However, the respondents disagreed on study habits dealing with not studying a few hours before the examination, as indicated by the mean of 2.45. This shows that students do not want to fail their exams, so they study a few hours before the examination.

Similar to the study of Bhat and Khandai (2016), poor study habits, on the other hand, do not work and do not assist pupils in achieving their studies.

Academic Performance of the Respondents

Table 3 presents the academic performance of the respondents during the first and second semesters of SY 2020-2021.

It can be observed from the table that the lowest rating is 2.30 while the highest rating is 1.35. These ratings manifest a mean of 1.58 and a standard deviation of 0.15.

Table 3. Academic Performance of the Respondents

GWA (Average of Two Semesters)	Lowest Rating	Highest Rating	Mean	Standard Deviation
	2.30	1.35	1.58	0.15

This means that online class is not a hindrance to having good grades in SY 2020-2021 as long as they have good habits that they apply in their study. This result coincides with Henriksen et al. (2020) study, which proved that students perform far better in online learning than in the traditional mode of learning.

Difference in the Study Habits of the Respondents when Grouped according to Sex

Table 4 displays the difference in the study habits of the respondents when they are grouped according to sex.

Based on the data, it can be gleaned that all of the indicators of study habits do not show a significant difference when respondents are grouped according to sex as indicated by their p-values that range from 0.11 to 0.97, which are higher than 0.05 significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

This means that there is no evidence of gender dominance concerning study habits. Both genders have a similar way of dealing with the new normal setup of education.

This result contradicts the study of Ossai (2012) and Saleem et al. (2020), in which they found out that female students seem to have better study habits than their male counterparts.

Moreover, the finding showed that there is no significant difference in the study habits of the respondents when they are grouped according to sex. The result validates the study findings of Awabil, Kolo, Bello, and Oliagbo (2013) who found no significant difference between male and female students in good study habit skills. However, the result of this study is in disagreement with another research study that showed that there was a significant difference in the skills of study habits on a gender basis (Ossai, 2012; Saleem et al., 2020).

Table 4. Difference in the Study Habits of the Respondents when Grouped according to Sex

Study Habits	Group Means		t-value	p-value
	Male	Female		
1. My study room is more spacious with good ventilation.	2.88	3.10	0.59	0.56
2. I do not feel comfortable reading in bed.	3.00	2.99	0.04	0.97
3. I have a chair and a desk in my study room.	2.75	3.04	0.78	0.44
4. I do not enjoy studying with music.	2.63	2.79	0.41	0.69
5. I take down important notes during virtual discussion.	3.50	3.49	0.06	0.96
6. I highlight important words or phrases in my book when studying.	3.13	3.40	0.99	0.32
7. I am able to study up to three hours or more in a day.	3.00	3.19	0.48	0.63
8. I do have a personal study time table.	2.63	3.20	1.62	0.11
9. I use my own words when taking down note.	3.50	3.37	0.42	0.68
10. I do not spend much time on social activities at the expense of my studies.	2.75	3.06	0.88	0.38
11. I do not study few hours before examination.	2.38	2.46	0.23	0.82
12. I study with my friends but with less verbal conversation.	2.88	2.87	0.01	0.99
13. I do not bother myself with personal problems when studying.	2.63	2.77	0.39	0.70
14. I never doze off when studying.	3.00	2.64	0.92	0.36
15. I am never attracted to the TV set and other family activities when studying.	2.88	2.49	1.08	0.28

Relationship between Study Habits of the Respondents and Their Academic Performance and Monthly Family Income

Table 5 displays the relationship between the study habits of the respondents in the new normal in terms of profile (age and monthly family income) and their academic performance. It shows the r-values and p-values of each study habit based on their profile and academic performance.

Study Habit and Monthly Income. Based on the data, only one descriptor of study habits dealing with having a more spacious and ventilated room suggests a significant relationship with the monthly income of the respondents since it has a p-value of 0.04, which is less than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the respondents that have higher family monthly income tend to have better study habits because of having a study room that is more spacious with good ventilation.

The result of the study validates the study of Razia (2015), who found out that adolescents from higher socioeconomic backgrounds have better study habits than those from lower socio-economic backgrounds. Correspondingly, one of the variables to consider in having effective study habits that impact student performance is the study environment. According to Kim (2013), a study environment includes a conducive and pleasant area for

students to study without noise or interruptions and study resources that are easily accessible to students. Students learn better if they are in a neat environment with readily available materials, and devoid of noise and distractions, so they can focus and think about academic problems whether at home or school.

Study Habit and Academic Performance. Based on the table, only one indicator of study habits dealing with having a chair and a desk in the study room appears to have a significant relationship with the respondents' academic performance. This is supported by its p-value of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected.

This means that higher academic performance is evident among respondents with a chair and a desk designated for educational activities in their study room.

It has a connection to the study of Vargas et al. (2020) which found out that students' desks/tables and chairs, as well as the technical equipment they use to study (tablet, cell phone, computer), are examples of such variables that have an impact on a higher academic achievement. Lighting, noise, and temperature are other factors.

Table 5. Relationship between Study Habits of the Respondents and Their Academic Performance and Monthly Family Income

	Study Habits	Monthly Income		Academic Performance	
		r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value
1.	My study room is more spacious with good ventilation.	0.23*	0.04	-0.15	0.18
2.	I do not feel comfortable reading in bed.	-0.09	0.44	0.05	0.68
3.	I have a chair and a desk in my study room.	0.11	0.35	0.23*	0.05
4.	I do not enjoy studying with music.	-0.16	0.17	0.05	0.69
5.	I take down important notes during virtual discussion.	-0.02	0.85	0.08	0.52
6.	I highlight important words or phrases in my book when studying.	-0.03	0.83	-0.09	0.45
7.	I am able to study up to three hours or more in a day.	-0.06	0.60	-0.02	0.85
8.	I do have a personal study time table.	0.12	0.30	0.01	0.98
9.	I use my own words when taking down note.	-0.07	0.53	-0.08	0.46
10.	I do not spend much time on social activities at the expense of my studies.	-0.07	0.57	-0.12	0.30
11.	I do not study few hours before examination.	0.14	0.21	-0.07	0.56
12.	I study with my friends but with less verbal conversation.	0.11	0.36	0.06	0.61
13.	I do not bother myself with personal problems when studying.	0.15	0.18	-0.14	0.24
14.	I never doze off when studying.	-0.04	0.70	0.06	0.63
15.	I am never attracted to the TV set and other family activities when studying.	0.01	0.94	0.09	0.41

Conclusions

Based on the significant findings, the following statements are concluded:

1. The respondents have good and skilled study habits in the new normal education.
2. There is no significant difference in the study habits of the respondents when they are grouped according to sex. There is no majority between males and females when it comes to study habits. It was found that the gender basis is not the determinant of the differences in study habits of the respondents. Both genders show a similar approach in dealing with the new normal setup of education.
3. There is a significant relationship existed between the study habits of the respondents in terms of their socio-economic status and academic performance. Based on the study's findings, it can be inferred that there is a significant and positive relationship between the study habits and the monthly income status of the parents of the respondents. The study proved that the higher the level of the monthly income of parents, the better their study habits. If study habits are satisfactory, it can be said confidently that the academic achievement of the respondents will also be on the higher side.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings brought about in the study, the following are recommended:

1. Students should have good study habits to have good academic performance. Based on the findings, study habits have a significant relationship to academic performance.
2. Parents should provide a chair and a desk for the study room of their child. Based on the study, higher academic performance is evident among respondents with a chair and a desk designated for educational activities in their study room.
3. Teachers should provide a copy of the lesson to the students. Based on the findings, respondents agreed that highlighting important words or phrases in virtual discussion is one of the effective study habits.
4. Teachers should maintain the strategies and practices in teaching. Based on the findings, respondents had a good academic performance during the new normal education.
5. Future researchers who will conduct more studies in relation to study habits and academic performance must extend to a larger sample.

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